

Peer learning: Professor and Students unite in a flexible bridging mathematics course

Morten Brekke, Luis Fernando Jack & Emma Nesdal Slinning

morten.brekke@uia.no ; luis.f.jack@uia.no ; emma.n.slinning@uia.no

University of Agder, Grimstad, Norway

Abstract

This contribution details the transformation of our six-week intensive mathematics course from a traditional on-campus format, featuring half-day lectures and training sessions with a final written exam, to a more flexible structure incorporating pre-recorded videos and a portfolio of digital tests, with a minimum passing requirement of 60% on all tests. The course is offered both on campus and online, emphasizing independent learning through self-paced study, digital resources, and interactive problem-solving sessions. The teaching was organized and conducted by three learning assistants who provided support and conducted lectures on demand. The course is designed to ensure a smooth transition to engineering mathematics, specifically Calculus 1. We aimed to compare the performance of students in Calculus 1 who completed this redesigned course with those who followed the traditional summer course. This paper presents the results of this comparison, along with insights from semi-structured interviews with both campus and online students to understand their experiences.

Introduction

As part of our efforts to recruit more students to the engineering program at our university, we offer a six-week intensive mathematics course, MA-006, every summer. This course is designed for students with university entrance qualifications who lack mathematics and for students with vocational certificates and it attracts between 130 – 150 students each year. Passing this course is a prerequisite for entering a bachelor's program in engineering. Previously, the course was taught in a traditional manner, with three hours of lectures and three hours of training with student assistants every day. The requirements to pass the course included three written midterm tests (above 40%) and a final written three-hour exam (above 40%). In 2024, I took over the course and implemented substantial changes. I had previously offered the same course online, demonstrating that students from these courses performed as well in engineering mathematics Calculus 1 as regular students with full specialization in mathematics (Brekke, 2014). Experience with flipped classrooms and portfolios with digital tests showed improvement for the bachelor's program in electronics (Brekke, 2016). The setup of the MA-006 course builds upon well-documented results. Ideas from educational research have shaped the design of the course, with a particular focus on how individual tasks are designed using STACK (Kinnear, 2018). *Retrieval practice*, such as the *testing effect*, shows that *"retrieval of information from memory produces better retention than restudying the same information for an*

equivalent amount of time" (Roediger & Butler, 2011). Therefore, we use *"test-enhanced learning"*, where tests are used as a tool to help students learn during the course (Brame & Biel, 2015).

We have also changed the Calculus 1 course from a traditional final written exam to portfolio assessment using STACK, with very good results. This change came after investigating how the teaching was done and how it was perceived by students (Zakariya et al., 2022). Our experience from these changes includes increased motivation, better self-regulation, and less test anxiety among students. We avoid procrastination, see more cooperation between students, and observe them spending more time on mathematics. We have extended the use of teaching assistants in our teaching. These are experienced students trained in guiding students and in basic pedagogy and didactics.

MA-006 was set up with pre-recorded short videos and a portfolio of three tests in the online assessment system STACK, with a requirement of a minimum of 60% on all tests to pass. The course is designed to provide a smooth transition to Calculus 1. MA-006 was offered both as a campus course and as a fully online course. The campus teaching was organized and conducted by three teaching assistants. The course emphasizes independent learning through self-paced study, digital resources, interactive problem-solving sessions on campus. It has an intensive format that requires students to have strong skills in self-regulation and stress management. Students must be able to organize their own learning, seek help when needed, and find a balance between rapid progression and understanding. Initially, students receive a suggested progress plan with tasks covering the curriculum and learning objectives. For each topic in the book, video lectures are provided and can be used as needed. Daily task reviews are conducted, where teachers go through tasks that students have found challenging. Students are assessed through three partial tests during the course, with each test allowing four attempts. The tests can be taken from any location within the specified time window, with all aids available. To pass the course, students must achieve at least 60% correct on each partial test.

Here, we Morten (professor and course responsible), Emma, and Luis (teaching assistants and fellow students) present how students experienced the course. We will show how this group of students performed in Calculus 1 compared to regular students and previous cohorts. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with both campus and online students to understand their experiences.

Method: Semi-structured interviews

To gain a deeper understanding of how students experienced the redesigned version of MA-006, we conducted a series of semi-structured interviews with students who completed the course during the summer of 2024. Our goal was to explore how the course structure, particularly its flexible format, peer-led support system, and digital assessment model was perceived by students, and how these elements influenced their motivation, engagement, and sense of mastery. We chose a qualitative approach, as we were not only interested in measuring outcomes but also in understanding why and how the course worked or didn't for individual students. The interviews followed a semi-structured format, meaning we prepared a set of guiding questions but allowed the conversation to flow naturally. This ensured consistency across interviews while leaving room for

individual perspectives, allowing for in-depth responses, follow-up questions, and reflection. The questions were designed to cover four main aspects:

1. **Academic experience:** This included the use of the textbook and video lectures, experiences with problem-solving sessions and peer instruction, and whether students felt ready to begin Calculus 1.
2. **Motivation:** We focused on how students managed their own learning (self-regulation) within a flexible course structure.
3. **Practical aspects:** This covered students' experiences with the STACK testing system, the use of video lectures as a learning tool, and the role of peer learning.
4. **Overall impressions of the course:** This included expectations, satisfaction, and perceived value of the learning experience.

We interviewed both students who attended campus daily and those who completed the course remotely. This distinction allowed us to identify differences in how the learning environment shaped their experiences. The students' backgrounds also varied in terms of previous mathematical education, which offered further insight into how accessible and effective the course was for a diverse group of students. All interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically, focusing on recurring patterns as well as outliers.

Students' perceptions

Several strong themes emerged from the data. Many students emphasized how helpful the teaching assistants were, especially because they were fellow students themselves. As one participant noted, *"It's much less intimidating to ask for help when you're talking to someone who's been in your shoes recently."* Another added, *"The assistants explained things in a way that made it click, and I didn't feel judged for not understanding right away."*

Students also reflected on their use of learning materials and tools. Most relied primarily on the course-provided resources, particularly the textbook and Canvas. Some made occasional use of external AI tools like ChatGPT and Symbolab to clarify difficult concepts. *"I used ChatGPT to explain concepts in simple terms when I got stuck,"* said one student, *"but I didn't trust it to actually do the math for me."*

Regarding the flexible nature of the course, responses varied. Several students thrived in the self-paced format, especially those with strong self-discipline. One student commented, *"It was motivating to follow the progress plan and check off tasks—I liked having control over my own learning."* However, others found it more challenging to stay on track without the structure of daily lectures, especially those studying from home. One online student noted, *"The flexibility made the course possible for me, but I did miss having people around me—it's easy to fall behind when you're alone."* Another student reflected, *"The flexibility was great, but it was also easy to say, 'I'll do it later' and then suddenly you're behind."*

From the mandatory course evaluation, we see in Table 1, that the overall feedback from students was positive. However, many found the pace and the workload overwhelming, as reflected in comments such as: *"A bit too much material for the available time"* and *"Very well-organized program. Although the workload was large and challenging, it was manageable thanks to a good plan and structured content on the Canvas page."*

	Average score (from 1 – 5, were 5 is best)
The work and teaching methods in the course contribute to a good understanding of the subject matter.	4.18
I perceive the course as relevant to my studies.	4.23
Teaching contributes to my academic development.	4.25
The work and teaching methods are varied and appropriate.	3.95
The use of digital tools in teaching contributes to effective learning.	4.29
Academic collaboration among students (in groups/study circles) contributes to a positive learning environment.	4.24
Academic collaboration between students and teaching assistants contributes to a positive learning environment.	4.27

Table 1 Student's feedback

Students' performance:

To determine if the changes made to the course had any effect on student performance, anonymous grade data was extracted from the university's database for the fall semesters of 2023 and 2024 for the Calculus 1 course. Students retaking the subject were not included in the analysis, as the focus was on first-time, first-year students.

The students were then categorized into "TRES" (summer course students) and "Ordinary" (regular students) based on their type of enrollment, and the frequency of each grade for the two groups was counted. As shown in Figure 1, this also includes a small number of students registered as "N/A," indicating registration but no participation from these students. While counted as a fail, these students are separated to provide a more realistic picture of the distribution of grades. It is important to note that some students enrolled as "TRES" are exempt from MA-006 due to previous education, creating some discrepancies in the data as they did not participate in the summer course. Although no definite data exists for the number of students this applies to, the difference in the number of students is between 5-6%, which is unlikely to significantly affect the data; average course size indicates this applies to between 5-10 students.

Figure 1. Students' performance data.

For both groups, a general increase in high grades and a reduction in students failing the course can be observed. Most significant is the reduction of fail grades among "TRES" students, falling from 21% to 11%. Overall, these numbers indicate a positive impact of the changes in course structure.

Conclusion and findings

Conclusions so far shows that teaching assistants, were valued for their approachability and understanding. Students relied heavily on course-provided materials and AI tools like ChatGPT for clarifying concepts. Motivation and self-discipline were crucial for success, with campus attendees finding the collaborative environment motivating. Students reported a smooth transition to Calculus 1, with no significant knowledge gaps. The course's intensity and segment-based testing system were particularly appreciated.

The opportunity for multiple attempts on the partial tests has encouraged students to take the tests without aids to see how well they understand the subject. The partial tests provide feedback on what they need to work on and the chance to improve their results immediately. The possibility of multiple attempts has also helped reduce stress levels in an otherwise hectic school environment. However, we see that the great freedom in the course also makes it possible to use AI. ChatGPT answered all the questions on a test and achieved 81% correct answers. In other words, it is possible to pass the course without working and without the necessary competence. However, this will not be possible when students start with university-level mathematics, where tests must be taken under supervision and without aids, something we have been clear about.

To evaluate the extent to which the course has been successful, we must first clarify our objectives. Are we aiming to educate the best students with deep understanding and high competence, or to make our engineering studies accessible to the widest possible range of students? This is a crucial discussion. If our goal is to educate the best students, we may need better control and more secure assessment methods. With the current structure, where students have significant freedom to use various aids such as ChatGPT, it is challenging to determine if the tests truly assess the students' individual knowledge and skills. Students who pass but lack a fundamental understanding of the subject may contribute to lower average grades and higher failure rates in subsequent mathematics courses. To ensure we are educating the best, we must develop assessment methods that minimize the risk of external aids distorting the results. On the other hand, if our overarching goal is to make engineering studies more accessible to a broader range of students, we are on the right track. The flexibility of the course allows more students to participate regardless of geographical location or other commitments. This accessibility enables students to adapt their learning to their own life situations, making education more inclusive and available to all who wish to participate. These two goals are not necessarily mutually exclusive, but they require different strategies and approaches. For future courses, we should consider how to balance the need to ensure high-quality education with the desire to include and support a diverse range of students. Regarding this course, our department's current strategy is to give students in the summer course the freedom to use all aids (to attract more students), rather than being strict. Students who choose to "cheat" their way through the summer course will be exposed in engineering mathematics, where tests must be taken under supervision in our newly built examination facility.

Finally, students have given positive feedback on the support from us teacher assistants. They have trusted that we master the course content, and they have appreciated the low threshold for asking questions.

The findings from these interviews not only inform our understanding of the student experience in MA-006 but also provide a valuable basis for further development of the course. As we prepare to offer MA-006 again next summer, insights from this research

will help us refine the course structure, improve student support, and strengthen the overall learning experience.

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